

Research Article

Vishwa Mukha Lepam Significant Role In Skin Complexion

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ABSTRACT

Nowdays, there's a worldwide trend towards the utilization of herbal merchandise and therefore the adoption of additional natural fashion. Herbal cosmetics are cosmetics containing a bioactive element or a medicine. The usage of Phytochemicals derived from a variety of botanicals serves two purposes :-

1. For the care of body and its elements.
2. The presence of botanic ingredients influence biological performances of skin and supply nutrients necessary for the healthy skin. Acne, blackheads, pimples and dark circles are very common among today's youth and people that suffer from it. Skin disorders are sometimes caused by blood pollutants, in line with Ayurveda, Impurities within the blood are the foremost common explanation of skin problems. Ayurveda describes a variety of herbs and remedies for blood purification. The herbal paste are used to cure skin conditions like pimples, scars, blemishes, facial hair reduce naturally and pigmentation on the face referred to as "Mukha lepa"(face pack) in Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

A great demand from Ayurveda in the field of cosmetology has been established due to its unique concept about beauty and effective, cheaper and long lasting beauty therapy without any side effect.

The herbal paste which is applied on face to treat acne, pimple, scars, marks and pigments are known as "mukha lepa" in Ayurveda. The present article is aimed to provide the details about the concept of mukha lepa, the drugs useful for

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improving complexion and for the common skin ailments. For this, the material was collected from the main classical texts and nighantus of Ayurveda including published scholarly articles. Overall it can be said that, it is always better to avoid synthetic, chemical based cosmetics products and use the natural substances and products for beautification. There are various kinds of face pack described in ayurveda based on climatic changes which have nourishing, healing, cleansing, astringent and antiseptic properties.

Composition

- MULETHI (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*)
- RAKT CHANDAN (*Pterocarpus santalinus*)
- SHWET CHANDAN (*Santalum album linn.*)
- KASTURI HALDI (*Curcuma aromatica*)
- INDIAN ROSE (*Rosa indica*)
- MANJISTHA (*Rubia cordifolia*)

- ORANGE PEEL POWDER (*Citrus sinensis*)
- RED MOONG (*Vigna radiata*)
- GRAM FLOUR (*Cicer arietinum*)

Properties Of Good Quality Of Mukha Lepa

1. The drugs should be uniformly mixed.
2. Sufficient liquid media should be added in preparation of face pack.
3. It should have pleasant odour.
4. It should produce a significant cleansing of skin.
5. It should be non toxic to the skin.
6. When applied to the face, it should dry out rapidly to form an adherent coating on face.
7. The coating should be removed by gentle washing and should not cause any discomfort to face.

Test Report Of Vishwa Mukha Lepam

CENTRAL LABORATORY
PATANJALI FOOD & HERBAL PARK PVT. LTD.

TEST REPORT

Report Control No.: CLR001274/24
Date: 10/07/2024

Customer Details

Vd. SHEKHAR SOLANKI
PATANJALI YOGPEETH PHASE - I
ROORKEE ROAD, HARIDWAR UTTARAKHAND

Sample Details

Lab Ref. No. : 24061401274

Sample Description as : VISWA MUKTA LEPAM
Mark on Sample : VISWA MUKTA LEPAM
Manufacturer Name : NA
Name of Supplier : NA
Mode of Collection of Sample : SUBMITTED BY CUSTOMER
Batch No. : NA
Date of Manufacture : N/A
Date of Expiry : NOT MENTIONED
Sample Quantity : 50GM
Date of Receipt of Sample : 14/06/2024
Analysis start date : 14/06/2024
Analysis completion Date : 10/07/2024

RESULTS

S.No.	Test Parameters	Units	Test Method	Results
1	Description	-	Visual	Fine powder
2	Colour	-	Organoleptic	Brown
3	Odour	-	Organoleptic	Characteristic
4	Acidity	%w/w	Fssai manual	0.76
5	pH (5 %)	-	API	5.78
6	Total fat	%w/w	API	2.59
7	Loss on Drying at 105°C	%w/w	API	7.05

End of Report

R. Sharma
10/07/24
RAJESH P. SHARMA
SR. CHEMIST
Authorized Signatory

1. Samples will be retained for 7 days from the date of issue of test report unless otherwise specified.
2. Test report in full or parts shall not be used for promotional or publicity purposes.
3. Results given in report are related to sample submitted.

Methods Of Lepa Application

The drugs should be uniformly mixed with water/gulabjala.

If skin is dry then add few drops of honey to the mixture.

Thickness Of Mukha Lepa

One fourth, one third and half angula pramana is the thickness of the lepa respectively for doshaghna lepa, vishaghna lepa and varnya lepa. (one angula= 1.5cm approx)

Time For Lepa Application

Lepa should not be applied at night nor should it be allowed to stay on after it dries up.

Direction Of Lepa Application

Lepa should be gently rubbed in an upward to opposite direction of hair over the skin to make the action of application and effective.

Procedure After Application Of Mukha Lepa

1. Lepa should be allowed to remain till it becomes dry; if left dry, it vitiates the complexion of the skin.
2. It should be removed after moistening and when removed, the face should be anointed with oil.
3. The person should avoid day sleep, exercise talk, exposure to fire and sunlight, sorrow and anger.

Contraindication And Mukha Lepa

1. It should not be applied to persons suffering from pinasa (rhinorrhoea), Arjirna (indigestion), immediately after Nasya Karma (nasal drop), Hanugraha (lock jaw), Arochaka (anorexia) and after keeping awake the previous night.

Benefits And Mukhlepa

If properly applied, it cures Vyanga (blackish hyper pigmentation of faces), wrinkles, acne, (yauvan pidika), Reduce facial hair growth, Nilika (bluish hyper pigmentation), lightening the spots and give clear glow skin.

CONCLUSION

Herbal face packs or masks are used to stimulate blood circulation, rejuvenates the muscles and

help to maintain the elasticity of the skin and remove dirt from skin pores. The recent interest of consumers in herbal cosmetics has been stimulated by the declines of faith in modern cosmetics, the belief that plant based cosmetics products are superiors to man-made synthetic cosmetics and the reference to successful historical used by different cultures. These reasons have contributed to the increased acceptance as well as manufacture of herbal cosmetics. Uses of Mukha Lepa increase beauty and imparts freshness. It is better to avoid synthetic chemical based cosmetics products and uses the natural substance and products. It will make skin healthy, prevent from skin diseases and improve complexion. Herbal face packs increases the fairness and smoothness of skin, also able to cure wrinkles, dark circles, pimples, reduce unwanted facial hair etc. In the global market, herbal formulations are in high demand. Thus, we tried to formulate a herbal face pack complying to all the guidelines suggested by the literature.

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